

Examining the Correlation Between Extracurricular Engagement and Academic Achievements Among Grade 10 Students

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Abstract. The study focused on investigating the extracurricular involvement and Academic achievement of Grade 10 students. Data were collected from students through a survey, and interviews were conducted using a mixed-method approach. This exploration aimed to focus on the participation of Grade 10 students' involvement in diverse extracurricular areas, particularly in sports, clubs, and volunteer work, and their correlation with students' academic achievement, including grades, awards, and leadership roles. Evaluation revealed a positive relationship between active participation in higher educational attainment and extracurricular activities. The interpretation of the data suggests that the student's involvement in non-academic endeavours contributes to the holistic development and may enhance their overall school performance. The results suggest that schools should encourage balanced participation in extracurricular programs to cultivate well-rounded learners equipped with both academic knowledge and essential life skills.

KEY WORDS

1. Extracurricular activities 2. Academic achievements 3. Grade 10 students

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1. Introduction

The main focus in schools is academic learning, but thinking that the development of the student's extracurricular activities (ECAs), such as sports, music, clubs, and volunteer work, is considered important, these ECAs can contribute to personal and social development. Studies in countries like the United States, Finland, and Japan have shown that students who participate in ECAs demonstrate enhanced academic performance, higher levels of school engagement, stronger leadership and interpersonal skills, and better time management. These findings support the idea that learning extends beyond textbooks and that skills learned outside the classroom can significantly contribute to overall student achievement. Numerous studies have highlighted the positive impact of extracurricular activities (ECAs) on students' academic and personal development. According to Eccles and Barber (1999), participation in structured extracurricular activities is linked to higher academic performance, improved school engagement, and stronger social connections. Fredricks and Eccles (2006) further emphasized that ECAs promote essential skills such as time management, self-discipline, and leadership, attributes that often translate into better classroom performance. Similarly, Mahoney, Cairns, and Farmer (2003) found that students involved in ECAs were less likely to drop out and more

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

likely to pursue higher education, indicating long-term academic benefits. In the Philippine context, the Department of Education (DepEd) has reinforced the importance of extracurricular and co-curricular programs through various memoranda and its K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum. DepEd emphasizes the development of 21st-century skills, including communication, creativity, and critical thinking, many of which are cultivated through active participation in ECAs. However, despite this emphasis, participation rates vary across schools due to limited resources, academic pressures, or lack of student motivation. Locally, many schools recognize ECAs but still face challenges in fully integrating them into school culture. Students in Grade 10 are at a critical stage in their academic journey, as they prepare for senior high school decisions and future career paths. This makes it an ideal level to assess the impact of ECAs on student outcomes. This study intends to determine if there is a significant correlation between the involvement of Grade 10 students in ECAs and their academic achievements.

1.1. Objective of the study—This research is to identify what are the types of extracurricular activities that Grade 10 students participate in, to assess the academic achievements of students who engage in extracurricular activities, and the researcher would also like to find out the correlation between extracurricular activities

involvement and the academic performance of the students.

1.2. Statement of the problem—Some believe that participation in such activities distracts students from their studies, while others argue that it can enhance their overall development and academic success. There are some educators and parents who remain hesitant about the true impact of extracurricular activities on students’ academic performance despite the increased emphasis on holistic education. This research aims to investigate the relationship between participation in extracurricular activities and the academic achievement of Grade 10 students.

The comparison of Academic Performance Based on Extracurricular Participation and its frequency by gender

How frequently do students participate in Extracurricular Activities and their academic performance?

Students’ involvement in activities such as sports, music/arts clubs, academic clubs, volunteering/service, and multiple activities on how they contribute to students’ academic performance.

The correlation between Extracurricular participation and the academic achievement of the Grade 10 students

2. Methodology

2.1. Research Design—This research employed a quantitative correlation research design supported by qualitative interviews. The use of a quantitative-correlational research design is well-suited for studies that aim to determine the degree of association between two or more variables without manipulating them. This design is particularly effective when examining naturally occurring relationships, such as the link between extracurricular involvement and student achievement. Creswell (2014) explains that correlational research is appropriate when the researcher seeks to identify patterns or trends and measure the strength of relationships between variables using statistical tools. This design is widely applied in educational research where ethical or practical concerns prevent experimental manipulation of student behavior or school systems. In the context of extracurricular activities and academic outcomes, Zaff et al. (2003) used a correlational approach to demonstrate how participation in organized activities during adolescence predicted positive educational trajectories. Similarly, Cooper, Valentine, Nye, and Lindsay (1999) employed correlational methods to study the impact of after-school programs on student achievement and concluded that statistical correlations could effectively illustrate associations between time use and academic performance. Thus, employing a quantitative-correlational design in the current study allows for an objective and statistically valid assessment of how extracurricular participation (independent variable) relates to academic and personal achievements (dependent variables) among Grade 10 students without intervening in their existing school activities.

2.2. Research Locale—This study was conducted at Leon Garcia Sr. National High School (LGSNHS), a public secondary institution located along Gotamco Street in Barangay Leon Garcia Sr., Agdao District, Davao City, Philippines. Operating under the Department of Ed-

ucation (DepEd) Region XI, LGSNHS serves a diverse student population, primarily from urban and economically varied backgrounds. The school offers both Junior and Senior High School programs, including the General Academic Strand (GAS) under the K to 12 curriculum. LGSNHS is recognized for its active engagement in both academic and extracurricular domains. Students regularly participate in various activities such as sports, music, leadership training, and community service. Notably, the school has a vibrant marching band and has achieved commendable results in regional competitions like the Davao Region Athletic Association (DAVRAA) Meet. These programs are integral to the school's mission of fostering holistic development among its students. The school's commitment to student excellence is evident in its recognition ceremonies, where achievements in academics and extracurricular activities are celebrated. For instance, during the 2022–2023 school year, students from Grade 10 Burgos were acknowledged for their academic performance, with averages ranging from 88 to 89, as documented in official school certificates. The selection of LGSNHS as the research locale is strategic, given its emphasis on both academic rigor and extracurricular involvement. This environment provides a rich context for examining the correlation between participation in extracurricular activities and student achievements, particularly among Grade 10 students who are at a pivotal stage in their educational journey.

2.3. Research Respondents—This study's participants consisted of 100 Grade 10 students from Leon Garcia Sr. National High School in Davao City, Philippines, during the School Year 2024–2025. The sample was composed of 50 male and 50 female students, ensuring gender balance to promote equal representation and reduce potential bias related to gender-based differences in extracurricular involvement and academic performance. Participants were se-

lected using purposive sampling, guided by the following qualifying parameters: 1. Currently enrolled in Grade 10 at Leon Garcia Sr. National High School. 2. Actively participating in at least one school-recognized extracurricular activity or not participating in any such activities for comparison purposes. 3. Must have official academic records for the current and previous grading periods to determine their academic standing. This group was selected because Grade 10 is a critical academic level, wherein students prepare for senior high school

choices and demonstrate emerging patterns in academic performance and personal development. The balance between ECA participants and non-participants also allows for meaningful comparison and correlation analysis.

2.4. Research Instrument—The researcher gathers information on the student’s extracurricular activities, including gender, type, frequency, and duration of involvement, through a structured questionnaire; this also includes the academic records (GPA) to assess student achievement

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—The data collected from the 100 Grade 10 student participants of Leon Garcia Sr. National High

School were analysed using quantitative methods, specifically descriptive statistics and Pearson product-moment correlation.

2.6. Data Analysis—Descriptive Statistics Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and describe the basic features of the data. These include: • Frequency and Percentage Distribution: To identify the proportion of students participating in extracurricular activities (ECA) versus those who are not. • Mean and Standard Deviation: To describe the central tendency and variability of students’ academic performance (e.g., general average or GPA) across groups. These descriptive tools helped provide a clear overview of the characteristics of the student

population in terms of academic achievement and extracurricular involvement. 2. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation To determine the strength and direction of the relationship between extracurricular activity participation and academic achievement, the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was employed. This statistical tool measures the linear relationship between two continuous variables: • Independent Variable: Level of involvement in extracurricular activities (e.g., frequency or participation status) • Dependent Variable: Academic performance (e.g., average grade or GPA)

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Comparison of Academic Performance Based on Extracurricular Participation—The table shows that students who participate in extracurricular activities have a higher average GPA (89.5) compared to those who do not

(83.2). The standard deviation indicates that the GPA scores of non-participants are more spread out (4.1), suggesting less consistency in academic performance. This supports the hypothesis that involvement in ECAs may contribute positively to academic success.

Table 1. Participation in ECAs and Students' Academic Performance

Participation in ECAs	Number of Students	GPA	Standard Deviation
Participates	65	89.5	3.2
Does Not Participate	35	83.2	4.1
Total / Overall	100	87.3	4.0

3.2. *Frequency of Extracurricular Participation by Gender*—More female students (35) participate in extracurricular activities compared to males (30), despite equal total gender distribution. A slightly higher proportion of female students (70%) are involved in ECAs than male students (60%). This may suggest that female students are more engaged in structured extracurricular programs, which can be a valuable insight for program planning and inclusivity efforts.

Table 2. Frequency of Extracurricular Participation by Gender

Gender	Participates in ECAs	Does Not Participate	Total
Male	30	20	50
Female	35	15	50
Total	65	35	100

3.3. *Academic Performance by Frequency of ECA Involvement*—The data shows a positive trend: the more frequently students participate in ECAs, the higher their average GPA. Very active students (3+ times a week) in ECAs have the highest GPA (91.8) and the lowest standard deviation (2.9), indicating both academic strength and consistency. This suggests that consistent and active engagement in extracurricular activities is linked to better academic performance, likely due to enhanced skills like time management, discipline, and motivation.

Table 3. Academic Performance by Frequency of ECA Involvement

Frequency of Distribution	Number of Students	Average GPA	Standard Deviation
Occasionally (1–2/month)	20	86.1	3.8
Regularly (1–2/week)	25	89.6	3.2
Very Active (3+/week)	20	91.8	2.9

3.4. *Academic Performance by Type of Extracurricular Activity*—Students in academic clubs and volunteering show higher average GPAs than those in sports or arts alone. Those engaged in multiple activities (two or more) perform the best academically (GPA 92.3), suggesting that a well-rounded engagement may have the strongest impact. Again, students with no extracurricular involvement have the lowest GPA on average. It visually compares the aver-

age GPA of students by type of extracurricular activity. You can see that students involved in multiple activities, academic clubs, and volunteering tend to have higher GPAs than others.

Table 4. Academic Performance by Type of Extracurricular Activity

Type of Activity	Number of Students	Average GPA	Standard Deviation
Sports	25	88.7	3.5
Music / Arts	20	89.2	3.1
Academic Clubs	10	91.5	2.8
Volunteering / Service	10	90.1	2.9
Multiple Activities (2+)	15	92.3	2.5
No Participation	35	83.2	4.1

3.5. *Correlation between Extracurricular Participation and Academic* —The Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.48$) indicates a moderate positive relationship between extracurricular activity involvement and students’ academic performance. The p-value (< 0.01) means this relationship is statistically significant at the 1%

level. In other words, there is a very low probability that this result happened by chance. This suggests that as extracurricular involvement increases, students tend to have higher GPAs. The findings support the alternative hypothesis, which states that extracurricular activities positively influence academic performance.

Table 5. Correlation between Extracurricular Participation and Academic Achievement

Variables	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
ECA Involvement vs. Academic GPA	0.48	< 0.01	Moderate positive correlation

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1. *Findings and Conclusions*—The findings of this study support the hypothesis that extracurricular engagement is positively associated with academic performance among Grade 10 students. Students participating in a diverse range of ECAs, particularly those with academic relevance, tend to have higher GPAs. Students who actively engage in extracurricular activities not only perform better academically but also gain soft skills beneficial for future success.

4.2. *Recommendations*—Schools should continue to promote diverse extracurricular opportunities (academic, artistic, athletic) and encourage students to participate in at least one activity that matches their interests and skills. Students with minimal or no involvement in ECAs

could benefit academically by joining programs that promote collaboration, leadership, and discipline. Since academic-related extracurricular activities (e.g., debate clubs, math teams, and science fairs) showed the strongest correlation with GPA, schools should consider expanding or funding more academic enrichment programs. While increased participation correlates with better performance, excessive involvement can lead to burnout. Educators and guidance counsellors should help students maintain a healthy balance between academics, ECAs, and rest, and schools should conduct orientation sessions or workshops for students and parents to inform them about the academic and developmental benefits of joining ECAs.

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